

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS : X-RAY ANALYSIS OF KCl DISSOLVED IN B_2O_3 -GLASS

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Further experimental evidence is adduced in support of the fact, first noticed by the authors that the spacing of polar crystals is enlarged when they are dissolved in a homogeneous glass. In the present paper, the spacing of KCl dissolved in boric oxide glass has been investigated and an enlargement of the spacing to the extent of about 36% over the normal value has been noticed. A tentative theory of the phenomenon is given.

Majumdar and Palit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 461) were the first to notice that a polar crystal like NaCl, when dissolved in a glass like boric oxide, still retained its crystalline form but the spacing was enlarged to the extent of over 60% of the normal value. According to the theory of polar crystals first put forward by Born and Lande (*Verhand. deuts. physikal. Gesellschaft*, 1918, 20, 210) and modified later by various workers, like London, Lennard Jones, Slater and Kirkwood and others, the equilibrium in a polar crystal is assumed to be the result of several forces, mainly two, namely the electrostatic or Coulomb forces between the oppositely charged ions, which obey the inverse square law and the short distance repulsive forces, which involve power of the radius higher than the two. The theoretical considerations in calculating lattice energy are all based upon the assumption that the medium intervening the charged particles in the crystal is a vacuum. In other words, the dielectric constant is taken as unity.

EXPERIMENTAL

As in the experiment with NaCl, recrystallised and dried KCl was mixed with specially dehydrated B_2O_3 and heated in a platinum crucible in an electric furnace for eight to ten hours until a thoroughly homogeneous melt was obtained. The crucible was then chilled when the melt cracked on solidification. The particles were taken out and the chlorine content volumetrically determined. Another sample was powdered and the Debye-Scherrer photograph was taken in the usual way.

Potassium metaborate was prepared according to the directions of Rosenheim and Leyer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 119, 1). About 18 g. of KOH and 64 g. of boric acid were dissolved in 45 c.c. of warm water. On cooling the solution in a freezing mixture, about 34 g. of the salt, KBO_3 , separated out. These crystals were dissolved in 30 c.c. of hot water and recrystallised. In this way about 11 g. of the pure salt were obtained. X-ray measurements were done in the same way as in the case of NaCl— B_2O_3 system (Majumdar and Palit, *loc. cit.*). An exposure of about twelve hours was given and the films developed. Fig. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 represent respectively the photographs with pure KCl, KBO_3 and three samples of KCl— B_2O_3 system.

As in the case with NaCl, B_2O_3 partly reacted with KCl forming KBO_3 , as indicated by common lines leaving considerable amounts of KCl dissolved in the glass. The percentage of KCl found by analysis corresponds to this dissolved chloride.

In the case of KCl reflections from odd planes are absent. Therefore the values $\text{Sin } \theta/\sqrt{4}$, $\text{Sin } \theta/\sqrt{8}$, $\text{Sin } \theta/\sqrt{12}$, $\text{Sin } \theta/\sqrt{16}$, etc. are calculated and the two constant values corresponding to K_α and K_β determined by trial. The lines due to the borate are eliminated by reference to its photograph. The value of a_0 is then calculated.

The following tables give the results of analysis of the different systems.

TABLE I

Intensity α	A. KCl (Fig. 1)								
	W	S	W	S	V.W.	S	W	W	V.W.
	3.85	4.21	5.42	6.03	6.7	7.45	8.7	9.82	10.9
Intensity α	B. KBO ₂ (Fig. 2)								
	W	W	W	W	W	W	W	W	W
	2.35	2.9	3.6	3.8	4.2	4.8			8.25

TABLE II

Intensity α	A. KCl (7.2%) dissolved in B ₂ O ₃ (Fig. 3)									
	S	W	W	S	S	S	W	W		
	2.35	2.7	2.87	3.3	3.65	3.62		4.0		
Intensity α	B. KCl (7.81%) dissolved in B ₂ O ₃ (Fig. 4)									
	W	S	S	W	W	W	W	W		
	4.2	4.4	4.76	5.23	5.55	6.3				
Intensity α	C. KCl (8.13%) dissolved in B ₂ O ₃ (Fig. 5)									
	S	W	W	S	S	S	S	W	W	
	2.35	2.7	2.9	3.3	3.6	3.6	4.4	4.8	5.55	6.3

In the photographs of KCl dissolved in B₂O₃, the lines due to KBO₂ are eliminated by referring to Table I B and the spacing of dissolved KCl calculated.

With pure KCl K_α is found to be 0.1264 and for K_β 0.1151. Hence a_0 for pure KCl works out with

$$K_\alpha, a_0 = \frac{1.539 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.1264} = 6.075 \text{ \AA}; \quad K_\beta, a_0 = \frac{1.389 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.1151} = 6.040 \text{ \AA},$$

the mean value being 6.056 Å. This is in agreement with the standard value 6.2 Å.

In the case of KCl dissolved in B₂O₃ glass, the spacing of the former is found to be almost independent of the salt concentration in the region of concentration investigated, and the constant is found to be 0.0942 with K_α and 0.0833 with K_β . Hence a_0 for KCl dissolved in B₂O₃ works out

$$\text{with } K_\alpha, a_0 = \frac{1.539 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.0942} = 8.163 \text{ \AA}; \quad \text{with } K_\beta, a_0 = \frac{1.389 \times 10^{-8}}{2 \times 0.0833} = 8.345 \text{ \AA}.$$

the mean value being 8.256 Å.

DISCUSSION

As in the case with NaCl, the spacing of KCl dissolved in B₂O₃ glass is found to be larger than in the normal salt, the extent of enlargement being about 36%, considerably

Figs. 1—5 in the photographs refer respectively to KCl (pure), KBO_2 (pure), KCl (7.2%) dissolved in B_2O_3 , KCl (7.81%) dissolved in B_2O_3 , and KCl (8.13%) dissolved in B_2O_3 .

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less than the corresponding value in the former case. Also the spacing is found to be independent of the KCl concentration.

It is well known, however, that slight changes of lattice distance are observed in the case of alloys in which a metallic atom displaces another from its position in the lattice producing a certain deformation of the units. But the change in such cases is never beyond a small percentage which is quite small compared with the large change observed by us. Experiments carried out by Randall, Rooksby and Cooper (*Z. Krist.*, 1930, 75, 196) on various glasses brought out the idea that the lattice constants of a crystal do not remain constant as the crystalline particles vary in size. Experiments on the so-called 'amorphous' carbon by Lowry and Bozerth (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1524) and by Randall and Rooksby (*Nature*, 1932, 129, 280) and Hofmann (*Ber.*, 1928, 59, 2433) also suggest the same conclusion. Lennard Jones (*Z. Krist.*, 1930, 75, 215) has given theoretical reasons for anticipating the results. He has calculated that for small crystals consisting of 500 units, the spacing is 5% greater than in the ordinary crystal. For crystals of five layers thick each way, the change calculated is 7% and for minute crystals consisting of 3 units each way it is 14%. In no case, however, the expansion of the lattice caused evidently by the modification of the mutual polarising forces, is greater than 10–15% and is therefore inadequate to explain the very large expansion suffered by the lattice. The reason therefore has to be sought for elsewhere.

The possibility of the formation of less known and comparatively unstable borates in the glass is not excluded. But even if the borates like $5B_2O_3, K_2O$ be formed, they are present in *such small quantities* that they would not give any pronounced diffraction lines. It has been found that a concentration of these salts in glass less than 5–10% will not give any diffraction pattern at all. Whether crystalline anhydrous boric oxide has been formed also requires explanation. It is unlikely that B_2O_3 -glass, which normally does not give any diffraction lines, should show strong devitrification when a salt like KCl is dissolved in it. Moreover, a similar system containing dissolved NaCl instead of KCl (Majumdar, & Palit, *loc. cit.*) did not show the same lines, which would have been the case if the extra lines were due to devitrified B_2O_3 . The matter is under further investigation.

About the weak lines with KBO_2 , it may be said that the same exposure (of about 12 hours) was given in each case including that of the borate. The weakness of the lines is not therefore due to smaller exposure but to greater absorption of X-rays by the salt.

A tentative explanation of the phenomenon is suggested below. When a crystal is made to dissolve in a glass melt and the latter allowed to solidify, very much the same type of forces will operate as if the crystal were present in a solution of lesser viscosity, like water, with the difference that the magnitude of some of the forces will be altered. On account of the altered dielectric, there will be a shielding of the electrostatic forces, bringing about a general weakening in their magnitude. The dielectric constant of the medium employed is about 3.5 (Thomas, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 85, 2109). It is natural to expect that the short distance repulsive forces will also be weakened to a certain extent by the shielding action of the altered dielectric, but these will not be probably weakened to the same extent as the purely electrostatic forces. Hence when the ions of the crystal take up their equilibrium positions in the lattice, they are shifted to a greater distance than would be the case if the crystallisation had taken place from the melt of the pure crystal

or from its aqueous solution. It may be added, however, that the dielectric constant is a macroscopic and not a microscopic term, representing as it does in some way or other, the total effect of the shielding which is produced on the component ions. Hence the explanation attempted must be regarded more or less qualitative, until it can be proved experimentally that the spacings of the same crystal dissolved in two glass media vary inversely as their dielectric constants.

The fact that concentration of KCl (7.2%, 7.8%, 8.13%) has practically no influence on the dimension of the space lattice also needs explanation. It is apparent that in the new space lattice of the alkali halide, its own concentration has no effect on the various forces within the system. It is believed by Warren, Zachariasen and others that in alkali borate glass, the alkali ions are situated within the hollows of the *non-periodic* network formed by the boron-oxygen-boron groupings. The alkali halide lattice in a glass of boron trioxide may therefore be supposed to be formed within the hollows of the network, the only effect on the alkali and the halogen ions being the shielding action produced by the immediate environment, which in this case consists of boron and oxygen atoms joined by purely co-valent linkages. The concentration of the alkali halide itself in such a scheme will have no effect on the arrangement of its own lattice. It will only modify the relative density of the salt within the glass. Most likely its distribution within the glass is not what we usually take to be homogeneous.

It has been noticed by Majumdar and Sarma (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 241) that alkali halides dissolved in boric oxide glass show the same deformation effect as would be required by Fajans' theory of deformation (Fajans and Joos, *Z. Physik*, 1923, 23, 1) with the modification that in the case of chlorides containing small cations like LiCl, the amount of deformation produced is very much greater than in corresponding aqueous solutions of the crystal. It has also been found that the amount of deformation produced progressively decreases with the increase in diameter of the cation. Thus in the system CsCl—B₂O₃, there is practically no change in the mol-refraction values from those of the crystals and dilute solution. It should be stated here that the results of X'ray analysis of the two cases, NaCl and KCl dissolved in B₂O₃ glass apparently indicate a change in the opposite sense. For, while in the case of NaCl, the increase in spacing amounts to 60%, in the case of KCl it is only 36%. Normally we can expect a stronger deformation in the case of NaCl.

Experiments are in progress to measure the spacing of RbCl and CsCl dissolved in the same medium.

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